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Cheating and Student's Learning and Achievement Motivation

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INTRODUCTION

Passing exams, writing essays and completing assignments in a way that conforms to the general expectations of academic integrity are at the heart of gaining a Bachelor's or Master's degree. An interested student seeking to learn and to achieve a high level of mastery is the faculty ideal, but what are the student's motives to learn and how do they cope with these requirements? Complaints continue to increase that students do not seek mastery but instead seek points or credit. Students don't ask the question: "What does that mean and how does it work?" They prefer to ask: "Do I have to learn this to pass the exam?"^[1] Two questions arise on the side of professors. The first is culturally pessimistic: "Which abilities and competencies has the new generation of graduates acquired when they leave the university to fulfil their future jobs? Furthermore, is it enough to know how to find the answer with google or is personal knowledge still necessary?" The second is more pragmatic: "How do we cope with those mere credit point collectors?" Or: "Do we have to disband the ideal of the motivated learner or is there a possibility to change teaching in a way that is catchy

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and enticing to the majority of students?” As Nicholls et al wrote in 1985 with regard to school children:^[2]

“Views about the purposes of education vary in the degree to which they represent school learning as an end in itself versus a means to an end.” (683)

When the grade is seen as an end, usually with the goal of getting a good job, mastery per se is not as valuable as credit points. Taking this into account, “cheating is a strategy that serves as a cognitive shortcut”.^[3, p. 2] Unfortunately, it is a promising strategy when detection rates are roughly one or two percent. Taking this further into account, we get to the somehow obvious conclusion: Student motivation and cheating behavior are closely connected. Therefore, we interviewed a sample of 683 students from various disciplines (engineering, social sciences and arts) to gain a deeper insight about the relation of the two.

1 STATE OF THE ART

1.1 The German discussion

Even though we complain in Germany about the fading image of the ideal student, the scientific community gives little attention to these questions from a research perspective. Especially the scientific literature in English shows a massive body of research addressing the topics of interest and motivation of student learners as well as aspects of academic integrity and the so-called cheating epidemic. Various texts have been cited several hundred times like those by Haines et al (1986)^[4], McCabe and various co-authors^[5] or one of the early contributions by Bowers^[6]. The German discussion of academic integrity differs significantly: A small number of papers has been published so far. Until today, cheating has mainly been an issue treated in the national newspapers' weekend features. An exception was the case the former Secretary of Defense Karl-Theodor zu Guttenberg who lost his PhD in 2011 as the result of a publicly debated case of plagiarism. The wisdom of the crowd detected, in a joint effort within a few weeks 1218 plagiarized text components on 371 of 393 pages of zu Guttenberg's PhD-Thesis.

The public discussion about the zu Guttenberg case lead to an encouraged effort to address the topic of plagiarism at all levels of academic education. Especially the heads of university libraries initiated a number of local activities to sensitize academia to an increasing problem. Some librarians had already written papers a few years earlier¹ to create consciousness regarding the problem of using the easy to copy and paste options. Other articles highlighted general problems of science and the value of scientific knowledge in an age of a plagiarism epidemic.

In everyday German academic discussion, we talk about cheating as a type of personal insult resulting from students' “poor judgement, weak will, or lack of character.”^[7] Till now the discussion missed various aspects raised in the English publications mentioned in the introduction: Individual or context factors? The teaching moment and the contribution of the professorial performance in class remained unexamined.

1.2 The American or English discussion

Research on academic dishonesty started much earlier in the English academic literature. Davis^[8] gives an overview about the research results beginning in 1941 with reported cheating rates of 23% which grew towards 38% and 49% at the end of the 1950s. Actual numbers are up to 70% and 80% of the students reporting one or another type of academic dishonesty. McCabe et al report 82% in 2003.^[5] Furthermore, we find a body of literature about reasons for cheating which were first recognized in the

psychological disposition of the individual student and later in contextual variables as well.

Gender, age, grade point average, or national culture were typical characteristics to analyze and identify typical students that cheat.^[9] The result revealed changing degrees of influences (strong, some or even none). None of the socio-demographic variables offers a stable and reliable statistical result. Cheating students do not show a uniform character, obviously different situations (classes) lead to different behaviors. We rarely find students or pupil who always cheat and some more who never cheat. In a different approach McCabe and Treviño concentrated especially on the importance of honor codes. Throughout their research, they found significantly lower rates of cheating in those institutions of higher education which strongly implemented honor codes. It is not enough to have an honor code in place, the whole institution has to live according to it, and faculty has to put emphasis on the relevance to comply with the honor codes. McCabe et al report 27% or 17% lower rates of cheating in institutions with honor codes.^[5] However, German Universities don't have a strong culture of honor codes in place, at least they can't rely on a long lasting tradition.

A second line of discussion since the 1990ies is the connection between types of students' learning motivation, individual goals, and cheating behavior.^{[7], [9]} Especially the learning motivation and the goals of the students became one main key aspect of analysis which we focused on in the present research. In the literature, various authors picked up Dweck's ^[10] differentiation of mastery goals or learning (developing ability) and achievement or performance goals (demonstrating ability or avoidance to show a lack of ability)^[2]

“Mastery goals focus the individual on the task at hand and relate especially to developing competency and gaining understanding and insight. Performance goals focus the individual on the self and relate especially to how ability is judged and how one performs, especially relative to others.” ^[11, p. 77]

A mastery goal orientation is the ideal for the faculty. Nevertheless not all students adhere to deep learning. The goal to demonstrate ability is often related to superficial learning strategies like rehearsals and memorization to be able to reproduce knowledge while writing a test.^[11] For example, feeding short term memory seems like a reasonable strategy considering particular types of tests. Reproduced isolated facts and numbers (multiple choice) are much easier to mark for the professor than long texts explaining contexts and relations. Therefore, in certain learning contexts these performance goals are suitable “... as long as mastery goals are also high.” But how can we guarantee that mastery goals are also held to a suitably high level? ^[11]

While a mastery goal orientation is typically linked with lower rates of cheating, the attitude of performance goals make the use of cheating behavior more likely.^[29] As a type of motivated behavior, the intention is to deliberately violate rules of academic integrity to gain an advantage and to do better than other students. Students can successfully violate these rules of academic behavior due to low detection rates. High rates and greater differences were reported by McCabe et al.^[5, p. 223] They distinguish between cheating on tests and plagiarism and other forms of cheating on homework. Taken together as “serious cheating on written work”, 56% (1990-1991) and 58% (1995-1996) of the students in non-honor code institutions reported such cheating activities while 47% (1990-1991) and 45% (1995-1996) of the interviewed students reported “serious test cheating”.

2 METHOD

This research project “Academic Integrity: Perceptions of German Students”² is one of few studies in Germany about academic integrity with a reliable sample size. It modifies a prior analysis which was carried out by one of the authors at the University of Applied Sciences Darmstadt (one of the biggest German Universities of Applied Sciences). The previous study in 2016 had a sample of 335 students from engineering, computing and social science courses.^[13] Most of the participating engineering and computer science students answered the questionnaire in courses of the general studies program. The social science students who participated answered it in one of their subject courses. The pen and paper questionnaire was handed to the students in class to be answered anonymously and collected directly afterwards. The response rate was 99% with 684 questionnaires included in the analysis (representing approx. 4.1% of the total student population).

Males (n=390; 57% - females: n=293) are underrepresented in the sample (the university has 63.6% male students). 290 students (43.5%) were freshmen the other 390 were in their second to fourth year of study. Overall 386 students (56.5%) came from technical programs (engineering and computing) while 297 (43.5%) students belong to the social sciences and arts departments. We tried to set up the sample in a way that allows us to analyze by gender, subject area (engineering and computing vs social sciences and arts), and freshmen vs. experienced students. Table 1 shows the distribution of the sample according to these variables. Only one of the combinations of the three variables in the cross-tabulation reveals a weak representation of n=21.

Table 1. Composition of the sample (total: n=684)

	Male		Female		Total
	Freshmen	experienced	Freshmen	experienced	
Engineering and Computing	n=40	n=258	n=21	n=57	n=376
Social Sciences and Arts	n=34	n=49	n=120	n=84	n=287
Total	n=74	n=297	n=141	n=141	n=663

In this paper we will focus on the learning and achievement motivation, the socio-demographic data, and the McCabe/Bowers scenarios^[14]. The scenarios were part of the set of cheating behaviors analyzed by Bowers^[6]. Selection criterion were the overlap with the scenarios used by McCabe et al. Therefore, the scenarios cover not all types of self-reported cheating behavior, but this set of scenarios was adopted in various projects in the past^[13].

The Scales for Learning and Achievement Motivation (SELLMO) were developed by Spinath et al.^[15] and are based on the work by Nicholls et al.^[2]. The 4 scales consist of 31 items asking for three types of learning motivation which are closely related to the work of Dweck^[10] or Midgley et al.^[11]. These orientations are mastery goals (goal to learn and understand), performance approach (good results on exam) and performance avoidance (avoid negative results). The fourth scale measures the degree of work avoidance. These scales developed by Spinath are the only tested scales available in German to analyse goal and motivational orientations. The scales

² The project was funded by the Center of Research and Development of the University of Applied Sciences Darmstadt. The authors thank Anjell Korb and Jessica Nowotka for feeding the computers with the pen and paper data and for doing important parts of the data analysis.

are available in two versions: an often-used version for pupils and a second rarely applied version for students which we choose.

3 RESULTS

Figure 1 gives an overview of the self-reported cheating behavior of all interviewees. Remarkable is the varying number of students reporting no cheating on the nine scenarios. While only 11% reported that they turned in a homework done by a classmate (sc. 7), 80% worked collaborative on an individual task (sc. 8). The scenario obviously describes a cheating behavior that is very widely accepted and not considered a severe form of academic dishonesty, it might be seen as an option to improve one's teamwork experience and abilities. Furthermore, one of the participating students said: "If we hadn't worked together we wouldn't have had a chance to accomplish the homework."

Fig. 1. Share of students reporting cheating activity for 9 single scenarios (n= 680 to 683)

By calculating an index summing up the answer-codes of the nine scenarios, we identified the share of students who reported no cheating at all. With nine scenarios and codes from 1=never to 5=always the index value 9 is calculated for those students answering that they never cheated in the past. The highest possible value is 45. Overall, 92.5% of the students reported at least one incidence of cheating. That is not surprising when looking at scenario 8. Excluding this scenario (it includes a very social and help-oriented component) reduces the number of students who report cheating to 85.4%. About 50% of all respondents rank between index-values of 10 and 15, the next 25% are up to values of 19. About 3% (21 students) report cheating that cumulates to an index value of 25 and more

By a factor analysis (principle component analysis, varimax rotation) we differentiate two factors with an explained variance of 52.07%. Factor 1 encompasses scenarios 1 to 4 (loading values: 0.693 to 0.856), while factor 2 (loading values: 0.638 to 0.786) includes scenarios 5 to 7 plus scenario 9. The remaining scenario 8 loads less strongly on both factors. The factors represent two different situations in the academic life. While the scenarios of factor 1 address the situation of tests or exams while being monitored, factor 2 includes the scenarios that describe academic misconduct when doing homework or writing essays. The scenario seems to be unspecific in relation to the two factors explaining why it loads on both.

Coming back to McCabe's^[5] analysis of cheating rates in exams and in homework we calculated two indices according to the variables of the two factors. While McCabe et al reported approx. 9 to 15% higher cheating rates, the results of this research are more concerning: Only 21% of all interviewees answered the four scenarios in a way that indicated no cheating (index value: 4), 54.5% had index-values between 5 and 8, 2% had values between 13 and 16 (25 Students). Looking at homework 45.9% didn't cheat in the past (index value: 4), another 45% had index values between 5 and 8, with 0.5% of all interviewees with index values above 13.

Checking for socio-demographic differences doesn't indicate strong results: Comparing means of the index values reveals [1] equal values for cheating on tests for both sexes and female students cheat slightly (statistically significant) less on homework. [2] Freshmen report somewhat higher cheating rates in tests. [3] Engineers cheat more on homework than students of social sciences.

Our general assumption was that the learning and goal orientation has a significant influence on cheating rates. Therefore, we analysed the data using a one-way ANOVA-test. We used the four SELLMO-scales and grouped the sample three groups: the overall central 66.6% of the interviewees are displayed as average in the Figure 2 and 3, those 16.6 with low and high values are named as below and above average.

Fig. 2. Cheating on Test

Fig. 3. Cheating on Homework

The two figures reveal a few surprising results. First: Those students who answered the SELLMO-scales indicating a strong tendency for work avoidance show significantly higher cheating rates. Especially tests are the home ground of academic misconduct. The other three goals show no significant differences between the cheating rates. Second: With considerably lower differences (just a 2.3 value-differences on the index for homework in comparison to nearly 9.2 value difference for tests) the degree of work avoidance has still an influence on cheating rates.

Looking at the results for the other scales shows only small and statistically, and in most cases, non-significant differences. For tests the range of the mean values of the cheating-index for all three goal and learning motivations starts at 9.4 and the highest value is 10.2. When it comes to homework the graphs in Figure 3 show a tendency of slightly higher cheating rates when performance approaches are tested. Mastery goals show the opposing trend: The stronger the mastery orientation the lower the cheating rate, a result that follows general expectations.

4 DISCUSSION

The disadvantage of the chosen approach is the missing option to identify clear motivational types. Each participant shows a mixture of all four types evaluated with the SELLMO-scales: we can't say: "Student XYZ is a person who avoids work or who seeks for mastery". The data allows us to identify those persons that indicate with their answers that they have e.g. strong tendencies toward performance goals. v. Yperen et al.^[12] asked interviewees to choose between options in a round-robin mode about their goals and orientations. The four options are shown in table 2. A real mastery approach is rare (13.7%). More than 70% follow an avoidance orientation.

Table 2. Percentages of dominant achievement goal in the domain of education.^[12]

Performance approach: „...to do better than others“	6.8%
Performance avoidance: „... not to do worse than others“	23.1 %
Mastery approach: „ to do better than I did before“	13.7%
Mastery avoidance „ not to do worse than I did before“	48.1%
No dominant goal	8.3%

The four SELLMO-scales^[15] ask for different attitudes: three scales test the learning motivation. The fourth scale (work avoidance) has to be seen differently, a difference that explains the three lines around the index-value 10 in figure 2 and 3 and the completely divergent graph shown with the yellow line. Students act in relation to the context. In some classes they thrive on mastery, in others on performance.^[11] The attitude of work avoidance appears to be a more general and stable attitude. It is not an adjustable trait changing in dependence of the situation.

Universities and their professors have to cope with cheating:

„The first class period of each new college term is a unique occurrence for teacher and students alike. As professors, we hope that these students will find our classes intellectually stimulating and rewarding, if not enjoyable. Standing in front of that sea of faces at the initial class session, another more sobering prediction can be made with no small degree of certainty. Some of these students will engage in, or at least attempt to engage, in actions that are academically dishonest.“^[8: pp.26]

And: Universities and their professors have to keep in mind, that cheating is a deliberate behavior applied in some context but not in all. Therefore, the teaching moment and the expectations we stress as teachers are important. Do we ask for mastery? And ... do we support students and their curiosity?

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